

Supplementary Information

CYB561 supports the neuroendocrine phenotype in castration-resistant prostate cancer

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Supplementary Figures

S1 Fig. Chronic steroid starvation of LNCaP cells induces NE transdifferentiated phenotype. (A) LNCaP cells were maintained in complete growth media (FBS) and charcoal steroid-stripped (CSS) media for 10 mo (chronic CSS; cCSS). Chronic steroid starvation increased *SYP* mRNA expression. (B) Representative images (200X magnification) of LNCaP-FBS and LNCaP-cCSS at 90 days of cell culture maintenance are shown. The LNCaP-cCSS cells developed long cytoplasmic extensions resembling a neuron-like morphology. Bars represent mean \pm SEM with statistical significance indicated by asterisks in Student's *t*-test (* $P < 0.05$).

S2 Fig. *In silico* gene expression analyses of selected neuropeptide receptor genes in PCa. Gene amplification frequency of the neuropeptide receptor genes: (A) gastrin releasing peptide receptor (*GRPR*), (B) calcitonin receptor like receptor (*CALCRL*), (C) neurotensin receptor 1 (*NTSR1*), (D) neuropeptide Y receptor (*NPY1R*), (E) vasopressin receptor 1A (*AVPR1A*) were examined in the different types of PCa using publicly available RNA-seq and microarray copy number data (25), and visualized using the online visualization tool cBioPortal (27, 34). All five genes examined have higher amplification frequencies in the more advanced CRPC and NEPC stages relative to early-stage PRAD.

S3 Fig. Basal expression of *CYB561* homologs in normal and PCa cell lines. (A) The duodenal *CYB561* homolog, *DCYTB*, shows high expression levels in the normal cell lines RWPE-1 and PNT1A. **(B)** The expression of lysosomal homolog, *LCYTB*, is similar across all cell lines analyzed. **(C)** The annotated tumor suppressor *101F6* exhibits high expression in LNCaP cells. Bars represent mean \pm SEM with statistically significant differences determined through one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post-hoc test ($P < 0.05$; means with the same letter are not statistically different).

S4 Fig. Analysis of androgen-dependent expression of *CYB561* and *PAM*. (A) DHT treatment of LNCaP cells grown for 48 hr in complete growth media (FBS) or acute charcoal steroid-stripped (aCSS) media induced *KLK3* mRNA expression which was abolished in the presence of Enzalutamide (+Enz) (one-way ANOVA; FBS: $P < 0.0001$; aCSS: $P < 0.0001$; Student's t -test; Veh: $P < 0.0001$; +Enz: $P = 0.0003$). (B) *CYB561* mRNA expression was not affected by hormone treatment in both media setups (one-way ANOVA; FBS: $P = 0.1483$; aCSS $P = 0.1546$). (C) *PAM* mRNA levels increased with aCSS (Student's t -test; Veh: $P < 0.0001$; DHT: $P = 0.003$; +Enz: $P = 0.0155$) relative to the cells grown in FBS. Treatment with DHT dampened the increase in *PAM* expression and this was reversed by Enz treatment (one-way ANOVA; aCSS: $P = 0.0281$). (D-F) *KLK3*, *CYB561*, and *PAM* mRNA expression were measured in LNCaP cells grown and maintained in complete growth media (FBS) or chronic charcoal steroid-stripped (cCSS) media for 10 mo. Maintenance in cCSS depleted the expression of (D) *KLK3* mRNA, (E) did not affect *CYB561* mRNA expression, and (F) increased *PAM* mRNA levels. Bars represent mean \pm SEM with statistically significant differences determined through one-way ANOVA for effect of hormone treatment within the same growth media followed by Tukey's post-hoc test ($P < 0.05$; means with the same letter are not statistically different) and Student's t -test for the individual effects of growth media between the same hormone treatment (# $P < 0.05$, ## $P < 0.01$, ### $P < 0.001$, and #### $P < 0.0001$), or for the effect of growth media (* $P < 0.0001$).

S5 Fig. Validation of CYB561 knockdown in LNCaP cells. (A) Effective CYB561 knockdown was achieved at the (A) mRNA level by 74.24% as determined by RT-qPCR that was reflected at (B) the protein level as determined by western blot analysis in LNCaP cells transduced with shCYB561 compared to the scrambled (scr) shRNA control. (C) Hormone treatment did not alter CYB561 expression in scr shRNA and shCYB561 cells. Bars represent mean \pm SEM with statistically significant differences determined through Student's *t*-test for the effect of CYB561 knockdown ($*P < 0.0001$) or the effect of CYB561 knockdown between the same hormone treatment ($\#P < 0.0001$).

S6 Fig. Depletion of CYB561 lowered the sensitivity of LNCaP to androgen-stimulated and Enz-mediated effects on cell proliferation. (A-C) Proliferation rates of transduced LNCaP cells upon hormone treatment were measured every 72 hr over the course of one week. Knockdown of *CYB561* reduced the proliferative effects of DHT at (A) 72 hr and (B) 120 hr post-hormone treatment. Interestingly, *CYB561* knockdown enhanced the repressive effect of Enz on cell proliferation at the (C) 168 hr timepoint. Data points and bars represent mean ± SEM with statistically significant differences determined through one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post-hoc test for effect of hormone treatment ($P < 0.05$; means with the same letter are not statistically different) and Student's *t*-test for the effect of *CYB561* knockdown between the same hormone treatment ($^{\#}P < 0.01$)

S7 Fig. *CHGA* mRNA expression decreases with *CYB561* knockdown.

LNCaP cells transduced with the scrambled (scr) shRNA control and sh*CYB561* were grown and maintained in complete media (control) or transdifferentiation media for 14 days. Transdifferentiation induced a slight increase in relative *CHGA* mRNA levels in scr control cells (two-way ANOVA; Treatment factor: $P = 0.0315$; Knockdown factor: $P = 0.0714$). Bars represent fold-change values \pm SEM of Δ Ct with statistically significant differences determined through two-way ANOVA for main effects of treatment and *CYB561* knockdown and Student's *t*-test for the individual effects of treatment within an shRNA type (* $P < 0.01$).

S8 Fig. Basal expression of iron-responsive genes (IRGs) in prostate cancer cell lines and effect of *CYB561* knockdown and transdifferentiation on total iron concentration and IRG expression in LNCaP cells. (A) *TFRC* mRNA is highly expressed in LNCaP, 22rv1, and PC-3 cancer cell lines compared to normal prostate epithelial models RWPE-1. (B) *FTH1* mRNA level is highest in PC-3 cells while (C) *FPN1* mRNA is highly expressed in PNT1A and 22rv1 cells. (D) LNCaP cells transduced with the scrambled (scr) shRNA control and sh*CYB561* were grown and maintained in complete media (control) or transdifferentiation media for 14 days followed by quantitation of total iron concentration and IRG expression. The total iron concentration of LNCaP cells increased with transdifferentiation and this effect was dampened with *CYB561* knockdown (two-way

ANOVA; Treatment factor: $P < 0.0001$; Knockdown factor: $P < 0.0001$). (E-F) Expression of IRGs was assessed in LNCaP maintained in complete growth media (FBS) control or chronic charcoal steroid-starved (cCSS). Chronic steroid starvation (E) did not affect *TFRC* mRNA levels but (F) led to an increase in *FTH1* mRNA expression. (G-H) LNCaP cells were treated with vehicle (Veh), 10 nM DHT, or 10 nM DHT plus 10 uM Enz for 24 hr before harvest for RT-qPCR analysis. (G) *TFRC* and (H) *FTH1* mRNA expression remained unchanged across all treatments. (I) *STEAP2* mRNA levels were measured in the transdifferentiated LNCaP cells by RT-qPCR. Transdifferentiation resulted in an increase in *STEAP2* expression which was not altered by *CYB561* knockdown (two-way ANOVA; Treatment factor: $P < 0.0001$; Knockdown factor: $P = 0.2520$). Bars represent mean \pm SEM with statistically significant differences determined through one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post-hoc test ($P < 0.05$; means with the same letter are not statistically different), or two-way ANOVA for main effects of media treatment and *CYB561* knockdown, and Student's *t*-test for the individual effects of media treatment ($*P < 0.001$, $**P < 0.0001$) and *CYB561* knockdown between the same treatment ($*P < 0.01$).

S9 Fig. Gene expression analysis and total iron concentration in *CYB561* knockdown PC-3 cells. (A-B) Validation of *CYB561* knockdown in PC-3 cells showed that (A) *CYB561* mRNA expression was reduced by 74.23% at the mRNA level which was (B) reflected at the level of protein expression in PC-3 cells transduced with sh*CYB561* compared to the scrambled (scr) shRNA control. Knockdown of *CYB561* (C) decreased *CHGA* mRNA expression but (D) did not affect total iron concentration in PC-3 cells. Bars represent mean \pm SEM for *CYB561* mRNA and total iron concentration plots while bars represent relative fold-change values \pm SEM of the computed $\Delta\Delta Ct$ values for *CHGA* plots. Statistically significant differences due to *CYB561* knockdown were determined through Student's *t*-test ($*P < 0.0001$)